

Towards Accurate 3D Positioning in Large-Scale Underwater Environments

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Abstract—An effective and reliable AUV (autonomous underwater vehicle) should be capable to carry out complex underwater maintenance and exploration tasks in complete autonomy. Unfortunately, the hostility of the underwater environment, combined with the lack of any communication infrastructure and global positioning, introduce important scientific challenges. In this paper, we introduce an underwater global positioning system for AUVs suitable for large-scale environments sparsely populated by man-made infrastructure. Our system relies on sonar and stereo camera data, by means of a novel deep descriptor for sonar images and a two-view pixel-wise voting network for 6DoF (Six degrees of freedom) object pose estimation, both trained on synthetically generated datasets. The global AUV position is then estimated by exploiting a probabilistic framework that fuses on-line the available sensor readings.

Index Terms—Marine Robotics, Range Sensing, Vision-Based Navigation, Localization

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater robots (UID, Underwater Inspection/Intervention Drones) represent essential tools for carrying out complex assembly and maintenance operations of plants in underwater environments. The growing interest in highly sustainable offshore energy hubs will make these tools even more important since they can carry out heavy but necessary operations in underwater environments in a totally safe way. AUVs could carry out such tasks also in a fully autonomous way, without the need for remote piloting and possibly without the need for a support vessel, with undoubted advantages from an economic, environmental and personnel safety point of view.

One of the biggest challenges in autonomous underwater navigation is the capability of the AUV to localize itself, since the GPS signal is obviously not available, while the USBL (Ultra-short baseline) acoustic positioning system, when available, can be unstable and very noisy. To address this task, we are developing innovative deep-learning-based perception front-ends designed to process data acquired by a multibeam sonar and a stereo camera. In particular, we are developing a global and compact descriptor computed on the incoming, real sonar images that can be compared with a database of descriptors, each one computed on synthetic sonar images acquired at known locations in the working area, to assess the current position estimate. Furthermore, we are developing an object pose estimation module that, using

Fig. 1. Example data extracted from Gazebo simulator with the plugin proposed in [1]. The top row shows an example of a waypoint for inspecting an underwater asset (left) that requires multiple viewpoints to be inspected completely (right). The bottom row shows an example of sonar reading from the simulator.

only a CAD model of the object and the AUV stereo camera input, is able to estimate the pose of an object w.r.t. (with respect to) the AUV in extremely challenging conditions.

Acquiring and annotating large amounts of underwater data is extremely expensive and time-consuming. To overcome this limitation, both modules are trained by using synthetic datasets, possibly tailored to the target environment with domain adaptation techniques.

The information coming from the perception front-ends is finally fused with the information coming from the INS/DVL (Inertial Navigation System/Doppler Velocity Log) sensor which equips the AUV by exploiting a graph-based positioning framework, to estimate and update the global pose of the AUV w.r.t. a provided map of a large-scale environment sparsely populated by man-made assets.

This system is developed in the context of a research project carried out by the University of Padua. It has the ambitious goal of providing AUVs with an advanced autonomous perception system capable of increasing their productivity and effectiveness.

In this short paper, we first introduce the use-case we are addressing, specifically the large-scale autonomous monitoring of underwater assets¹, then we will briefly introduce the

¹An asset is any man-made underwater structure.

Fig. 2. Example of an underwater infrastructure planimetry (left); Example of the CAD model of an asset (right).

front-end modules and the probabilistic framework we are developing for AUV positioning.

II. THE AUVs AND A TYPICAL USE-CASE

In this section, we briefly introduce the AUVs that will be equipped with the presented positioning system along with a typical use-case addressed by such vehicles.

A. Description of the AUVs

In this project we are using two complementary UIDs², both designed to be remotely controlled from the ground in ROV (remotely operated vehicle) mode or to operate in a fully autonomous way in AUV mode. The first AUV is equipped with a double anthropomorphic arm and is suitable for targeted interventions such as maintenance operations on plants. It is supplied by a battery pack with 12 hours of autonomy and has a range of over 10 km. The second AUV is indicated for monitoring operations such as performing autonomous visual inspection while tracking pipelines and/or hovering around structures. Both AUVs are equipped with, among others, the following sensors:

- Forward-looking stereo camera;
- Forward-looking multibeam sonar;
- INS/DVL positioning system;
- Altimeter

High-performance embedded computers ensure the ability to process sensory data on board.

B. Large-Scale Autonomous Monitoring Use-Case

One of the typical missions an AUV should be able to accomplish is visually and instrumentally inspect a set of assets in a wide underwater area (Fig. 1). Due to the large distances, during these operations the communications with the support vessel are often minimal or absent, making remote piloting difficult or impossible, hence the ability to navigate autonomously is essential here. Large-scale autonomous monitoring represents the first use-case we want to tackle to validate the proposed positioning system. In this use case, the AUV should be able to autonomously and safely navigate from its garage toward a field of interest (and vice versa),

²For intellectual property issues, we currently cannot show images of the used AUVs.

Fig. 3. Our sonar image descriptor can be used to effectively compare the current sonar reading with other sonar readings in a database taken at different poses to assess what is the most likely position (e.g., poses A, B, C, ..., in red, w.r.t. an asset, in black) in which the AUV is currently located (left). Example of how the space around an asset could be sampled in order to produce the simulated sonar reading for the dataset construction (right).

populated with assets (infrastructures) that should be periodically visually and instrumentally inspected. During inspection operations, the AUV should circumnavigate every asset of interest at different altitudes and different distances, collecting all the required data without colliding with other objects. Altitudes and different distances may depend also on the current environmental conditions, e.g., water turbidity. An approximate field map (e.g., Fig. 2, left) and approximate CAD models of each asset of interest (e.g., Fig. 2, right) are provided as input.

III. SONAR IMAGE GLOBAL DESCRIPTOR

Due to the light absorption and turbidity, the use of cameras is strongly limited in underwater environments. The sonar, instead, is not affected by these disturbances making it the most reliable sensor for underwater localization [2] [3] [4]. The multibeam sonar installed in the AUVs (see Sec. II-A) acquires real-time sonar images with a 120-degree pan and 10-degree tilt field of view (e.g., see Fig. 4), making it an ideal sensor for obstacle avoidance, target detection, and close-range inspection in poor visibility environments. Unfortunately, due to nuisance phenomena such as multipath and cross-sensitivity, sonar images are rather noisy and not easily comparable between them, e.g., for image-based place recognition purposes. The place recognition problem aims to recognize known places within the environment despite changes in lighting, appearance, and small variations in point of view. This problem is usually addressed by comparing, in an efficient way, the current sensor reading, or a more compact representation of it, with a database of sensor readings, taken in known locations. To this end, we aim to introduce a compact global descriptor of the sonar images, to be compared with a database of descriptors, each one computed on sonar images acquired at known locations in the working area. The similarity between descriptors should encode the proximity of the locations where they were taken (e.g., Fig. 3, left). In our approach, we follow a basic framework that is typically exploited for deep descriptor computation (e.g., [5]). We compute the descriptor of the sonar reading as the embeddings of a convolutional

Fig. 4. Visualization of the triplet loss, for example, applied to sonar images. The triplet loss learns a descriptor that makes similar images spatially close and different images spatially distant.

neural network (CNN) fed with the sonar image. The CNN is trained over a large dataset of sonar images by using a *triplet loss* (see Fig. 4). Each data item is composed by a reference sonar image (called anchor), a sonar image acquired close to the pose where the anchor image was acquired (called positive), and an image acquired far from the pose where the anchor was acquired (called negative). The triplet loss aims to minimize the distance between the descriptors of the anchor and the positive while maximizing the distance between the descriptor of the anchor and the negative. To avoid the need to acquire an extended dataset with a real AUV, the training dataset is synthetically generated by exploiting the assumptions that the AUV moves in an environment sparsely populated by man-made infrastructure and that the map of the environment and the CAD model of the assets are given (see Sec. II-B). We render the underwater environment using the Gazebo simulator, while the sonar images are generated by using the multibeam sonar simulator proposed in [1] (e.g., Fig. 1). The training dataset can be produced by sampling the space around each asset with a regular grid (e.g., Fig. 3) and by storing for each cell the sonar image along with the related cell pose.

IV. TWO-VIEW 6DOF OBJECT POSE ESTIMATION

In this section, we describe our generator of synthetic underwater images that allows training our stereo-based object pose estimator.

A. Synthetic Dataset Generation with Synthetic-to-Real Domain Adaptation

Acquiring and manually annotating large amounts of underwater data is extremely expensive and time-consuming; still, deep-learning techniques require large amounts of data to be properly trained. To this end we developed:

- a synthetic dataset generation module with domain adaptation capabilities, producing large amounts of synthetic images closely reproducing the disturbances present in the real underwater environment;
- an image restoration module to visually enhance images taken in underwater conditions (or synthetically generated

Fig. 5. from left to right: real image of an underwater asset - generated synthetic image - synthetic image after adaptation

with the same intent) in order to facilitate further image processing operations.

The dataset generation module takes as input the CAD model of the asset and a dataset of clean underwater background images and produces “clean” samples by rendering the asset over the background images with a random pose and surface color. Then, real underwater images and the synthetic samples are processed by a CycleGAN [6] network in order to apply the same visual effects present in the real images to the synthetic ones. Qualitative results can be seen in Fig. 5.

When using both real and synthetic underwater images we encounter poor visibility, color loss, poor contrast, low definition of the immortalized asset, and an exponential attenuation of light as the distance from the camera increases; all these effects make applications such as object detection extremely difficult or even impossible. To make object detection and pose estimation feasible, we employ an image restoration module that enhances object visibility. This module takes as input an image affected by underwater distortion and produces an RGB image where two channels are obtained by applying CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization) with two different contrast clipping thresholds, while the third is the edge map extracted using HED [7] (holistically-nested edge detection). This process enhances contrast and highlights edges to better identify the framed asset.

With the discussed dataset generation pipeline, we are able to train the deep pose estimators of Sec. IV-B on restored synthetic images and use the limited amount of real underwater samples to evaluate the models’ performance (after applying restoration).

B. Pixel-wise Voting Network

Given the challenging working conditions posed by the effects of light distortion and turbidity affecting the acquired stereo images, we propose a multi-view pose estimation technique that combines deep learning with robust consensus algorithms. In particular, we extend the monocular robust pose estimator PVNet [8] (pixel-wise voting network for 6DoF pose estimation) to the stereo domain. Assuming that the CAD model of the asset to localize is available, PVNet defines a set of control points (keypoints) on the model and trains a deep convolutional network to predict the position of the projected keypoints in the input image; then the 2D-3D correspondences between the projected and model keypoints are aligned by a PnP [9] (perspective-n-point) solver to predict the pose of the object. The robustness of this approach comes from the module predicting the projected keypoints’ location: instead of directly regressing the position of each keypoint, PVNet

Fig. 6. PVNet pose estimation pipeline

learns to predict, for each pixel of the input image belonging to the object, a vector pointing to each keypoint in the image. In this way, it is possible to leverage a robust consensus algorithm such as RANSAC [10] (random sample consensus) to extract the keypoint’s location from the intersection of two or more pixels’ prediction, along with a confidence metric for each keypoint based on the votes’ variance. A schematic representation of PVNet’s pipeline is shown in Fig. 6

For the purpose of extending the PVNet architecture to the stereo domain we developed:

- an iterative weighted multi-view PnP solver jointly optimizing the pose from the prediction on both views by leveraging epipolar geometry constraints, weighted by the inverse of the variance of each prediction;
- an extension of PVNet processing the two views independently and fusing the results using the joint solver as in the previous point;
- an extension of PVNet processing the two views as a single 6-channel image from the beginning and predicting keypoints’ locations for both views, which are again fused using the joint solver discussed in the first point.

V. MULTI HYPOTHESIS POSE GRAPH-BASED GLOBAL POSITIONING

As introduced, our positioning system is composed of two main parts: the perception front-end (Sec. III and Sec. IV) and a pose estimation back-end. The former processes raw information from the sensors in order to produce estimates of the pose, while the latter fuses the different measurements in order to optimize the estimates of the poses. Still, measurements generated by the front-ends could be outliers, and the presence of these elements in the back-end makes the pose estimator to provide wrong solutions. Especially in poor and repetitive environments, such as underwater, sensor aliasing is the main cause of failure for front-end algorithms; this means that the back-end needs to be able to handle the cases in which the front-ends fail [11] and select/keep the measurements that are more likely to be correct. Building upon a standard pose-graph-based positioning and mapping framework [12], we propose a method that is based on Pairwise Consistent Measurements [13]: the central idea of this method is that the

majority of the measurements are inliers, and measurements that strongly disagree with previously accepted measurements are likely to be outliers. The algorithm proposed is greedy: it means that instead of keeping all the possible measurements until the end and then finding the most likely set of inlier measurements, it will perform a decision every time a measurement is going to be added, and determine if it is an outlier or not. Being greedy allows avoiding exponential growth in the complexity of the optimization, while at the cost of a negligible amount of accuracy.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this short paper, we presented the main ideas of our positioning system for AUVs moving in large-scale underwater environments. Our system exploits two novel perception modules for sonar-based place recognition and for multi-view object pose estimation, both trained on synthetically generated datasets. The output of these modules is fused into a multi-hypotheses probabilistic framework. Preliminary qualitative experiments on real data are supporting our intuitions.

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